

Supplementary material for
**Do near-field cues enhance the plausibility
of non-individual binaural rendering
in a dynamic multimodal virtual acoustic scene?**

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Contents

1	Additional figures	1
2	Matlab material	12
3	Video material	12

1 Additional figures

Figure S1: Low-frequency ($f < 3$ kHz) horizontal plane ILDs (left) and ITDs (right) for the synthesized near-field HRTFs (solid lines) and measured Neumann KU100 near-field HRTFs from [1] (dashed lines) at selected distances. The ILDs and ITDs of the synthesized and measured HRTFs are nearly identical, confirming that the synthesis yields correct results.

Figure S2: Magnitude response of the employed loudspeaker filter describing the on-axis frequency response of the JBL Clip+ loudspeaker and of the employed headphone compensation filter for equalizing the Sennheiser HD600 - Neumann KU100 binaural chain.

Figure S3: Two-dimensional histograms of the individual relative tracking data from Experiment 1 pooled over each participant's trials. The plot shows the frequency distribution of the sound source position relative to the participants' head in the horizontal plane, defined by azimuth and distance, as well as the individual p_{2AFC} value.

Figure S4: Two-dimensional histograms of the individual relative tracking data from Experiment 2 pooled over each participant's trials. The plot shows the frequency distribution of the sound source position relative to the participants' head in the horizontal plane, defined by azimuth and distance, as well as the individual p_{2AFC} value.

Figure S5: Two-dimensional histograms of individual relative tracking data from Experiment 1 pooled over the respective 25 trials of subjects 1 to 4 (S1–S4) in each of the four epochs (E1–E4). The plot shows for each epoch the frequency distribution of the sound source position relative to the participants’ head in the horizontal plane, defined by azimuth and distance.

Figure S6: Two-dimensional histograms of individual relative tracking data from Experiment 1 pooled over the respective 25 trials of subjects 5 to 8 (S5–S8) in each of the four epochs (E1–E4). The plot shows for each epoch the frequency distribution of the sound source position relative to the participants’ head in the horizontal plane, defined by azimuth and distance.

Figure S7: Two-dimensional histograms of individual relative tracking data from Experiment 1 pooled over the respective 25 trials of subjects 9 to 12 (S9–S12) in each of the four epochs (E1–E4). The plot shows for each epoch the frequency distribution of the sound source position relative to the participants’ head in the horizontal plane, defined by azimuth and distance.

Figure S8: Two-dimensional histograms of individual relative tracking data from Experiment 1 pooled over the respective 25 trials of subjects 13 to 16 (S13–S16) in each of the four epochs (E1–E4). The plot shows for each epoch the frequency distribution of the sound source position relative to the participants' head in the horizontal plane, defined by azimuth and distance.

Figure S9: Two-dimensional histograms of individual relative tracking data from Experiment 2 pooled over the respective 25 trials of subjects 1 to 4 (S1–S4) in each of the four epochs (E1–E4). The plot shows for each epoch the frequency distribution of the sound source position relative to the participants' head in the horizontal plane, defined by azimuth and distance.

Figure S10: Two-dimensional histograms of individual relative tracking data from Experiment 2 pooled over the respective 25 trials of subjects 5 to 8 (S5–S8) in each of the four epochs (E1–E4). The plot shows for each epoch the frequency distribution of the sound source position relative to the participants’ head in the horizontal plane, defined by azimuth and distance.

Figure S11: Two-dimensional histograms of individual relative tracking data from Experiment 2 pooled over the respective 25 trials of subjects 9 to 12 (S9–S12) in each of the four epochs (E1–E4). The plot shows for each epoch the frequency distribution of the sound source position relative to the participants’ head in the horizontal plane, defined by azimuth and distance.

Figure S12: Two-dimensional histograms of individual relative tracking data from Experiment 2 pooled over the respective 25 trials of subjects 13 to 16 (S13–S16) in each of the four epochs (E1–E4). The plot shows for each epoch the frequency distribution of the sound source position relative to the participants’ head in the horizontal plane, defined by azimuth and distance.

2 Matlab material

The Matlab script `ActaAcust_5_55_genHRIR.m` allows to synthesize the near- and far-field HRTFs, design the filter combining the headphone-compensation filter and the on-axis frequency response filter of the loudspeaker, and generate the filtered noise and speech test signals for Experiment 1 and 2. The sub-folder `filter` contains the headphone-compensation and loudspeaker filters. The sub-folder `testSignals` contains the pink noise burst sequence used for Experiment 1 and the speech sequence used for Experiment 2. To synthesize the near-field HRTFs, the SUPDEq toolbox¹ is required, providing the `supdeq_dvf.m` and `supdeq_parallax.m` functions for distance variation as well as various routines for (SH-based) HRTF processing.

3 Video material

The video `ActaAcust_5_55_Video.mp4` illustrates the experimental procedure using two trials of Experiment 1 as examples. It shows a participant moving the loudspeaker along the prescribed trajectory as well as the graphical user interface providing visual feedback of the participant's movement (as presented in the first and second training session). The audio corresponds to the recorded output of the binaural renderer. Note, however, that the audio output is equalized for the Sennheiser HD600 headphones used in the experiments.

References

- [1] J. M. Arend, A. Neidhardt, and C. Pörschmann, "Measurement and Perceptual Evaluation of a Spherical Near-Field HRTF Set," in *Proceedings of the 29th Tonmeistertagung - VDT International Convention, Cologne, Germany*, pp. 356–363, 2016.

¹Available: <https://www.github.com/AudioGroupCologne/SUPDEq>